

AFFECTIVE COMPONENT AND EMOTIONAL REACTIONS TO ACADEMIC AND CLASSROOM PERFORMANCE OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL PUPILS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 28

Issue 2

Pages: 98-105

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2649

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14207609

Manuscript Accepted: 10-14-2024

Affective Component and Emotional Reactions to Academic and Classroom Performance of Elementary School Pupils

Cherry May M. Villamor, * Emmauel Alex Bercero
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The study attempted to determine the extent of affective component of learning and emotional reactions to pupils' academic and classroom performance. Descriptive-correlational research method was utilized and the Statistical tools used in the study were mean, standard deviation, frequency and percentages, and Pearson-Product Moment Correlation were utilized to ascertain the extent of affective component and emotional reactions of pupils, pupils' academic and classroom performance, and for the significant relationship between the level of pupils' academic and classroom performance and the extent of affective components and emotional reactions of pupils. Findings revealed that affective components and emotional reaction to pupils' academic and classroom performance had moderate positive relationship. Subsequently, it was recommended that teachers should craft intervention materials that enhance psycho-emotional development of pupils in order to sustain academic and classroom performance.

Keywords: *affective components of learning, emotional reactions to academic and class performance*

Introduction

Pupils' engagements and participation in class tasks are influenced by the affective components and emotional reactions to the tasks given by teachers. Affective components include student motivation, attitudes, perceptions and values. Teachers can increase their effectiveness by considering the affective domain in planning the lessons, its presentation, and activities which stimulate pupils' interest and engagements.

The framework of this study is bounded on the context of legal and philosophical underpinnings pursuant to D.O 7, s. 2009 also known as guidelines for the effective implementation of the Elementary Curriculum which highlights the integration of socio-emotional learning which includes the core skills like self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship skills, and responsible decision-making. These skills will facilitate academic achievements.

The development of pupils' affective behavior indicates the emotional content in an interactions and therefore promotes an understanding and relationships. The affective component of pupils' emotional reactions to academic and classroom performance teaches them crucial life skills including the ability to understand themselves, develop a positive self-image, take responsibility for their actions, and forge relationships with the people around them.

Garcia, et al (2020) asserted that pupils' emotional reactions to task is an important affective component for the pupils' engagement in class tasks and activities. Pupils' task anxiety is the most frequent affective variable related to pupil performance and achievement. Further, it was also pointed out that pupils with higher anxiety level have low self-esteem and are emotionally unstable and can adversely influence pupils' academic and class performance.

Additionally, emotions are inherently linked to and influence cognitive skills such as attention, memory, executive function, decision-making, critical thinking, problem-solving and regulation, all of these play a key role to pupils' academic and classroom performance.

Stephens (2020) avowed that academic emotions affect pupils' attention, motivation, self-regulation and interest in the content. Pupils with high positive emotions during study could concentrate more on their tasks and are more motivated to learn and help increase their academic and classroom performance.

Subsequently, Ames (2019) purported that pupils' emotional reactions during learning have been shown to relate to a number of important educational and life outcomes. These findings are not surprising as the school environment creates a context for a variety of emotional experiences that have the potential to influence creates a context for a variety of emotional experiences that have the potential to influence teachers' instructional practices and students' learning processes.

Consequently, Bandalos, et al (2020) found out that pupils' anxiety or fear of negative results of teachers' evaluation on their performance tasks may result to poor work engagements, collaboration, and participation. In addition, pupils who are occupied with the thoughts of performing the tasks effectively like focusing on the content, planning to organize the activities, and encourage fellow learners to collaborate in work effort will be motivated to perform the tasks effectively and cognitions are elicited.

Kolb (2020) describes learning and classroom performance as a continuous process grounded in experience followed by perceptions, cognition and change in behavior. Accordingly, pupils engage in an experience, while perception and cognition are found to happen during the reflection when pupils are given the opportunity to reflect upon thoughts, emotions and behavioral actions.

Consequently, it was emphasized that pupils' academic and class performance is the result of active engagement different activities

and the interplay between emotions, cognition, and experiences. Pupils with affective component of attitude relates to feelings and emotions in their shaping on attitudes to the tasks which means that if the pupils feel more positive about doing a task, then they are more likely to perform them more effectively and proficiently.

However, there are motivational factors that teachers should consider in stimulating pupils to perform academically such as pupils' anxiety and teachers' responsibility for establishing a psychologically supportive learning environment. It is based on this circumstance that the researcher is motivated to conduct this study to ascertain the gap between pupils' affective component and emotional reactions to academic and class performance.

Research Questions

The study ascertained the effect of affective component and emotional reactions to academic and classroom performance of elementary school pupils in West City Central School of the City Division of Cagayan de Oro for the school year 2023 - 2024. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of affective component of learning and emotional reactions of Grade 3 pupils of West City Central School?
2. What is the level of academic and classroom performance of Grade 3 pupils when they are categorized as:
 - 2.1. outstanding;
 - 2.2. very satisfactory;
 - 2.3. satisfactory;
 - 2.4. fairly satisfactory; and,
 - 2.5. did not meet expectations?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the level of academic and classroom performance and the extent of affective component and emotional reactions of grade 3 pupils?

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized the descriptive-correlational research design. Descriptive research according to Calderon, et al (2019) is a fact-finding inquiry or investigation. It is employed to develop a thorough knowledge of the primary causes of the given situations.

In addition, descriptive-correlational design as an inquiry used an in-depth analysis of the problem which data collection methods include, but not limited to the survey questionnaire and the like.

Subsequently, descriptive-correlational research design is used to quantify the problem by way of generating numerical data or data that can be transformed into usable statistics. This method measures variables through the use of quantifiable or finite data and the analysis was based on generated information from statistical tools. This method is also used in an inquiry with larger population.

Successively, descriptive data gathering procedures comprise different types of gathering information such as, but not limited to, the use of adopted survey questionnaires.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the select Grade 3 pupils of West City Central School of the City Division of Cagayan de Oro. There were one hundred and sixty-five (165) pupil-respondents of the study who answered the survey questionnaire on affective component and emotional reactions to academic and classroom performance. The respondents were selected through a random sampling procedure.

Instrument

The study utilized a survey questionnaire adopted from Garcia, et al (2020) on affective components and emotional reactions of pupils in their academic and classroom performance.

The survey instrument is composed of three (3) major parts. The first part is on the affective component of learning with twenty (20) indicators. Second part is on emotional reactions of pupils with twenty (20) indicators. Part three is on the academic and classroom performance of grade 3 pupils which are categorized as outstanding, very satisfactory, satisfactory, fairly satisfactory, and did not meet expectations.

Procedure

The researcher asked permission from the Schools Division Superintendent through the recommendation of the Dean of the Graduate School and thesis adviser to conduct the study in the City Division of Cagayan de Oro.

The same permission shall be asked by the researcher from the parents of Grade 3 pupils to permit the researcher to use the pupils as subject-respondents of the study. However, the parents were assured that the data gathered from the survey questionnaire be treated to its highest confidentiality and be used for educational purposes only.

After the respondents provided the data, the researcher retrieved the said questionnaire, summarized, tabulated; and submit for analysis to the Statistician using appropriate statistical tools and techniques.

Data Analysis

The following statistical treatment were utilized in the study;

Problem 1. Mean value and standard deviation were used to present the extent of affective components and emotional reactions of grade 3 pupils.

Problem 2. Frequency counts and percentages were used to present the level of pupils’ academic and classroom performance.

Problem 3. Pearson-Product Moment Correlation was utilized to ascertain significant relationship between the level of pupils’ academic and classroom performance and the extent of affective components and emotional reactions to learning.

Results and Discussion

This section comprises the analysis, presentation, and interpretation of the finding resulting from this study on affective component of learning and emotional reactions to academic and classroom performance of Grade 3 pupils. The analysis and interpretation of data is carried out based on the results of a survey questionnaire in lieu of the problems presented.

Problem1. What is the extent of affective component of learning and emotional reactions to academic and classroom performance of Grade 3 pupils?

Affective component of learning is associated with how pupils feel and value learning and all other human values associated with them. It emphasizes the relevance of creating within themselves the environment that supports their affective and emotional processes which help encourage them to actively engage and be the active participants in learning.

Researches revealed that teachers play an indispensable role in the development of the affective school environment as an integral part of teaching-learning relationship which lead to both affective and cognitive skills development.

Table 1.1 presents the mean distribution of the affective component of learning to pupils’ academic and classroom performance.

Table 1.1. Mean Distribution of Affective Component of Learning to Pupils’ Academic and Classroom Performance

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>
1. Class performance tasks are interesting.	2.99	1.25	Sometimes
2. Class performance tasks are disturbing.	3.97	1.10	Most of the time
3. Class performance tasks are encouraging	4.38	.598	Always
4. Class performance tasks help develop positive attitude towards learning.	4.39	.590	Always
5. Class performance tasks help develop feelings of gratification.	4.39	.590	Always
6. Class performance tasks provide feeling of emotional reactions.	4.31	.723	Always
7. Class performance tasks provide bearing on behavior on learning and ability to learn.	4.38	.598	Always
8. Class performance tasks provide stimuli or motivate pupils to learn.	4.34	.684	Always
9. Class performance tasks provide pupil’s satisfaction or frustration.	4.39	.590	Always
10. Class performance tasks allow pupils to construct and understand reality.	4.38	.598	Always
11. Class performance tasks allow pupils to determine how problems are tackled.	4.38	.732	Always
12. Class performance tasks provide opportunity for the child to realize that subject has little application to real world.	4.32	.599	Always
13. Class performance tasks provide pupil with affective load with respect to confidence, self-worth, and attribution to success and failure.	4.38	.644	Always
14. Class performance tasks make pupil feel competent and trust their capabilities.	4.35	.598	Always
15. Class performance tasks allow pupil to feel accept success and failures.	4.38	.598	Always
16. Class performance tasks train pupil to develop confidence and willingness to work for achievement.	4.38	.598	Always
17. Class performance tasks allow pupil to involve in learning process.	4.38	.598	Always
18. Class performance tasks allow pupils to trust their own ability.	4.38	.598	Always
19. Class performance tasks train pupils to take responsibility in learning.	4.38	.598	Always
20. Class performance tasks develop pupil capacity to overcome or adapt to adverse situations.	4.38	.598	Always
Overall Mean	4.28	.674	Always

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Always/3.41-4.20 Most of the Time/2.61-3.40 Sometimes/2.81-2.50 Seldom/1.00-1.80 Never

Table 1.1 displays the mean distribution of affective component of learning to pupils’ academic and classroom performance. Overall, the respondents rated affective component of learning as “Always” with a mean of 4.28 (SD=.674). This result indicates that respondents always observed that class performance tasks provide support in the development of their affective component of learning. The emotion a pupil experiences is determined by the circumstance that triggers the emotion.

Leary, et al (2020) pointed out that affective component of learning means the emotional aspects of student learning and the human values associated with them. It emphasizes the importance of creating an effective environment that promotes active participation and

interest in the learning process which influences development.

The indicators “class performance tasks help develop positive attitude towards learning”, “class performance tasks help develop feelings of gratification”, and “Class performance tasks provide pupils’ satisfaction or frustration” obtained the highest mean value of 4.39 (SD=4.39) which is verbally described as “always” and is interpreted as “Very Highly Observed”. These findings indicate that class performance provided by teachers help develop pupils’ attitude towards learning, feelings of gratification or fulfillment, and the feelings of satisfaction, fulfillment, and frustration.

Valentina, et al (2022) averred that affective components of learning is an integral to the teaching-learning relationship, as it facilitates the establishment of affective bonds between learners and teachers which lead to cognitive and affective development.

It was also emphasized that without the establishment of these affective and emotional bonds, pupils may struggle to learn or may experience difficulty to learn. In a similar investigation, Leary, et al (2020) suggest that affective components of learning and emotional schema play an important role in learning development as it fosters holistic growth and self-fulfillment in learners by promoting emotional well-being and human values in the education process.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 2.99 (SD=1.25) is verbally described as “Sometimes” in the indicator “class performance tasks are interesting”. The result implies that only occasionally the respondents believed that class performance tasks are interesting. It can also be inferred based on findings that teachers need to make their class activities interesting and engaging because pupils tend to find them more engaging and challenging if class performance tasks involve real-world activities.

Olina, et al (2020) pointed out that teachers who provide interesting class performance recognized that class performance tasks play a pivotal role in shaping the cognitive processes, memory retention and decision-making among learners. It was also emphasized that affective learning involves creating an environment that fosters positive emotions such as inquisitiveness, curiosity, and enthusiasm which help enhance learning outcomes.

Table 1.2. Mean Distribution of Emotional Reactions of Pupils to Academic and Classroom Performance

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
1. Class activities provoke critical analysis	4.38	.598	Always
2. Class activities provoke pessimism	4.32	.709	Most of the time
3. Class activities provoke depression	4.28	.788	Always
4. Class activities provoke anger.	4.28	.788	Always
5. Class activities provoke fear.	4.14	.943	Most of the Time
6. Class activities provoke tension.	3.11	1.33	Sometimes
7. Class activities provoke sadness.	2.63	1.14	Sometimes
8. Class activities provoke worry.	2.37	.972	Seldom
9. Class activities provoke hate	2.30	.927	Seldom
10. Class activities provoke anxiety.	2.31	.934	Seldom
11. Class activities provoke despair.	2.30	.927	Seldom
12. Class activities provoke nervousness.	2.30	.927	Seldom
13. Class activities provoke uncertainty.	2.30	.927	Seldom
14. Class activities provoke contempt.	2.30	.927	Seldom
15. Class activities provoke frustration.	2.30	.927	Seldom
16. Class activities provoke pride.	2.30	.927	Seldom
17. Class activities provoke fun.	2.47	2.44	Seldom
18. Class activities provoke tranquility.	2.30	.928	Seldom
19. Class activities provoke enthusiasm.	2.30	.927	Seldom
20. Class activities provoke satisfaction.	2.30	.927	Seldom
Overall Mean	2.86	1.04	Sometimes

Legend: 4.21-5.00 Always/3.41-4.20 Most of the Time/2.61-3.40 Sometimes/2.81-2.50 Seldom/1.00-1.80 Never

Table 1.2 displays the mean distribution of emotional reaction to pupils’ academic and classroom performance. Overall, the respondents rated emotional reactions to academic and classroom performance as “Sometimes” with a mean of 2.86 (SD=1.04). This result indicates that respondents sometimes or occasionally observed that class performance tasks provide support in the development of their emotional reactions. The emotion a pupil experiences is determined by the circumstance that triggers the feeling, sentiments, and emotions.

Leary, et al (2020) purported that emotions affect pupils’ academic and classroom performance because pupils’ learning and the human values are associated with them. It emphasizes the importance of creating an effective environment that promotes active participation and interest in the learning process which influences development.

The indicator “class activities provoke critical analysis” obtained the highest mean value of 4.38 (SD=.598) which is verbally described as “always” and is interpreted as “Very Highly Observed”. This finding indicates that pupils’ academic and classroom performance was influenced by the class activities provided by teachers that provoke or develop pupils’ critical analysis. It can be inferred based on findings that the class activities involve thinking widely about an issue in order to develop a deep understanding and a point of view in

relation to the issue which help pupils improve performance both in their academic activities and in classroom engagements.

Valentina, et al (2022) suggest that pupils' emotional reactions to classroom activities is determined by the circumstance that triggers pupils' emotions. Pupils tend to be happy and internally motivated if they achieve better grades and were recognized by teachers which, according to research, help improve performance.

On the contrary, the lowest mean of 2.30 (SD= .927) is verbally described as "Seldom" in the indicators "class activities provoke hate, despair, nervousness, uncertainty, contempt, frustration, pride, tranquility, enthusiasm, and satisfaction". It can be inferred based on findings that class activities rarely introduced by teachers to promote hate, despair among pupils, nervousness and uncertainty, pride and serenity as well as passion but instead it was introduced to develop pupils' academic and classroom performance.

Olina, et al (2020) averred that pupils' emotion reactions to academic and classroom performance are kind of academic emotional experiences that pupils feel in learning situations. It was revealed that pupils with higher academic emotional reactions the higher is their arousal emotions to learn and excel in class activities.

Problem 2. What is the level of academic and classroom performance of grade 3 pupils when they are categorized as: Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Fairly Satisfactory, and Did not meet expectations?

Academic and classroom performance are predictive of pupils' affective and emotional development because it creates an affective environment that promotes active participation in academic activities in as much it improves pupils' interest in learning.

Table 2 presents the frequency and percentages of pupils' academic and classroom performance which are categorized as Outstanding, Very Satisfactory, Satisfactory, Fairly Satisfactory, and Did not meet Expectations.

Table 2. Frequency Distribution of Pupils' Academic and Classroom Performance

Pupils' Academic & School Performance	Frequency	Percentage
Outstanding	51	28%
Very Satisfactory	62	34%
Satisfactory	58	31%
Fairly Satisfactory	13	7%
Did not meet expectation	0	0%
Total	184	100%

As seen, 62 (34%) of grade 3 pupils achieved "Very Satisfactory" in their academic and school performance. This finding implies that there were more grade 3 pupils who performed remarkably and were adept in learning. It was also inferred that reasonable number of grade 3 pupils performed better in their academic and school activities. Thus, it is imperative for teachers to provide class performance tasks that develop the affective and emotional skills of pupils in order to effectively learn in school.

Leary, et al (2020) avowed that affective and emotional development among learners is associated to academic and classroom performance because an affective school classroom creates a learning-effective environment that promotes pupils' learning engagements and academic performance.

On the contrary, 13 (7%) indicates that the respondents manifest a "Fairly Satisfactory" academic and classroom performance. This implies that only few grade school pupils have fairly satisfactory performance. Pupils impartially performed their school and academic activities, they can work reasonably in their school and academic performance tasks. Barrera (2022) avowed that pupils who less developed their affective and emotional skills cannot perform well in their school and academic activities because they cannot associate and relate well with other learners.

Problem 3. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of affective component of learning and emotional reactions to pupils' academic and classroom performance?

Affective components of learning and emotional reactions are said to significantly associated to pupils' academic and classroom performance. Affective and emotional components are said to be help influence their academic and classroom performance. Researchers revealed that an affective classroom promotes pupils' learning engagements and encourage better performance. Affective learning is demonstrated by behaviors indicating attitudes of awareness, learning interest, attention, concern, and responsibility and interact with others which are appropriate to enhance pupils' motivation to learn.

Table 3 presents the test of relationship between the level of pupils' academic and classroom performance and the extent of affective components and emotional reactions of grade 3 pupils.

Table 3 displays the results of the test of relationship between pupils' academic and classroom performance and the affective components of learning and emotional reactions of pupils. Results revealed that affective component of learning has a "Moderately positive relationship" to pupils' academic and classroom performance ($r=.693$) as indicated in the probability value of .000. This result indicates that pupils' academic and classroom performance was influenced by pupils' affective development. Thus, the null hypothesis which states that "There is no significant relationship between the level of pupils' academic and classroom performance and the extent of affective components is rejected.

Table 3. *Test of Relationship between Pupils' Academic and Classroom Performance and the Extent of Affective Component and Emotional Reactions of Pupils*

Components of Learning	Pupils' Academic & Classroom Performance			
	(r)	Probability Value Sig. (2 tailed)	Interpretation	Decision on Ho1
Affective Component	.693	.000	Moderately Positive relationship	Rejected
Emotional Reactions	.595	.000	Moderately Positive Relationship	Rejected

*significant at $p < 0.05$ alpha level

Table 3 displays the results of the test of relationship between pupils' academic and classroom performance and the affective components of learning and emotional reactions of pupils. Results revealed that affective component of learning has a "Moderately positive relationship" to pupils' academic and classroom performance ($r = .693$) as indicated in the probability value of .000. This result indicates that pupils' academic and classroom performance was influenced by pupils' affective development. Thus, the null hypothesis which states that "There is no significant relationship between the level of pupils' academic and classroom performance and the extent of affective components is rejected.

It can be inferred based on findings that class performance develops pupils' affective skills which influence their performance in academic and school activities. Carpenter and Cepeda (2020) asserted that pupils' academic and classroom performance are influenced by pupils' affective development and maturity which help facilitates the establishment of affective bonds between learners and teachers which lead to cognitive and affective development.

Moreover, emotional reactions of pupils have a "Moderately positive relationship" to pupils' academic and classroom performance ($r = .595$) as indicated in probability value of .000. This result implies that pupils' academic and classroom performance are significantly predictive of the pupils' emotional reactions to learning. Thus, the null hypothesis which states that "there is no significant relationship between the level of pupils' academic and classroom performance and the extent of emotional reactions of pupils was rejected because it was found out that pupils' emotional reactions had positive relationship to their academic and classroom performance.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

Affective components of learning represent skills that foster appropriate emotional responses. The affective learning domain involves pupils' emotions toward learning and how that develops as learning progresses from the basic skills development such as listening, reading, comprehension, speaking to higher order learning process such as resolving issues and making decision which require affective and emotional skills and responses. Further, affective components of learning allow pupils to deal with things emotionally such as feelings, values, appreciation, enthusiasms, motivation and attitudes.

Pupils' emotions towards learning activates interest, curiosity, wonder, passion, creativity, engagement, and joy. This will also activate pupils' brain to make classroom experiences desirable and meaningful. Emotions aid pupils to focus attention to classroom activities.

Affective components of learning and pupils' emotional reactions in learning influenced academic and learning performance. Pupils with positive emotions to learning are linked to better retention of information and activities that challenge the brain to learn which facilitate in improving learning performance.

Based on the findings and conclusions presented, the following recommendations are suggested:

Department of Education (DepEd) Officials will provide development framework to intensify pupils' affective component of learning and emotional reactions to pupils' academic performance such as encouraging teachers to craft a psycho-emotional intervention materials to improve pupils' affective and emotional maturity.

School Principals/School Heads will be able to provide technical assistance to teachers in crafting psycho-social-emotional intervention materials which provide scaffolding in developing pupils' affective and emotional components to be more resilient in their academic activities especially in the mastery specific learning competencies

Teachers as Instructional Leaders are recommended to develop their strategic intervention materials responsive to the affective and emotional maturity of their learners. Said intervention learning materials will encourage pupils to appreciate learning and improve performance.

Parents will be able to provide support in the learning activities designed by teachers to improve their child's academic and learning performance. Parental support is indispensable in the academic success of their children, thus, the need to always encourage them to participate and collaborate with teachers in providing necessary learning support.

Community Officials/Other stakeholders will be able to intensify their support to school and learners especially in intensifying psycho-emotional scaffolding framework or programs in order to develop resiliency among learners in addressing all the challenges in school and in learning.

Future Researchers will be encouraged to conduct a similar study on the influence of affective or emotional components to pupils' learning and academic performance so that they may be able generate a doable framework responsive to emotional development and maturity of learners which stimulates school and learning performance.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Cherry May M. Villamor

Department of Education

Cagayan de Oro City – Philippines

Dr. Emmanuel Alex Bercero

St. Peter's College – Philippines